

Damage induced plasticity and low velocity impact behavior of composites

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Abstract

An elasto plastic damage model for fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) composites is proposed. The model has the capability to accurately predict the inter-laminar damage and the inelastic deformation of laminate subjected to low velocity impact loads. A user defined subroutine is developed and finite element (FE) simulations are performed using a commercial software ABAQUS/Explicit. The match between maximum contact force and delamination area predictions with the test data available in literature demonstrated good capability of the proposed model. The delamination is simulated by modeling the cohesive surface interaction between two adjacent plies. The simulations are also performed with the elastic damage model and the comparative assessment of the delamination area as well as the maximum contact force with plastic damage model and experiments signify the importance of modeling the inelasticity in the low velocity impact simulations.

1 INTRODUCTION

During their service life fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) may experience transverse load due to the impact by a foreign object which at microscopic level can cause fiber breakage, matrix cracking or delamination. The micro-scale damage sometimes is not visible and easy to detect but shows up on the surface of laminate as a permanent indent, the maximum value of which is generally used as a measure of the severity of impact damage. The occurrence of a permanent indent is an indication of inelastic deformation. The permanent deformation in a composite plate is caused by the micro debris formed due to material damage as observed by Bouvet et al.[1] who conducted an experiment with 25 J impact energy on a laminate. The debris settled between the delamination/matrix cracking area and prevented the structure from regaining its original position leading to residual plastic deformation of the laminate on unloading.

Numerical simulation of low velocity impact (LVI) use meso-scale approach and implement inter-laminar and intra-laminar damage through elastic damage mechanics based material models and ignore inelastic strains. The authors [2] have recently shown that inclusion of inelastic strains in the constitutive law can considerably improve displacement-time predictions of the target although force-time predictions even in absence of inelastic deformation are quite good.

In the present paper the predictions of delamination area using both elastic and inelastic models are made and compared with experimental results in literature.

Delamination is an inter-laminar damage and occurs due to failure of resin rich layer that exists between two adjacent plies. In last decade, this has been simulated mainly by using a cohesive surface governed by a traction-separation law between two adjacent plies. The crack formation starts at a certain level of tractions and the progressive decohesion is simulated by using a constitutive law which relates relative displacement of ply surfaces with the cohesive tractions. These cohesive tractions are directly linked with the stress level existing in the plies which in turn depends on whether an elastic or inelastic constitutive law is used to model them. Earlier Amyrich et al. [3] used cohesive interface elements to simulate the delamination in the laminates subjected to low velocity impact. The inter-laminar elastic damage model was able to predict the size, shape and location of decohesion region under wide range of impact energies. Chen et al.[4] proposed a model which was able to predict the inelastic deformations as well as inter-laminar damage successfully. Sun and Chen[4] used a single parameter plastic potential was for modeling the growth of plastic yield surface which starts to build from zero strain value. The cohesive elements were used between the plies to simulate the delamination and the plies were modeled using shell elements. The inelastic behavior of a laminate has been report for a lamina under pure shear load. Van Paepegam[5] used an exponential plastic stress-strain relation and a phenomenological damage growth laws to express this behavior. No consideration was given to inter-laminar damage region.

In the present paper a continuum damage mechanics based constitutive model is proposed which not only predicts the inelastic strains but also has the better delamination prediction capability. Three dimensional potential function is used for the growth of plastic surface in the effective stress space. The effectiveness of proposed model is also checked by performing the comparative assessment with elastic damage model. The results show the importance of consideration of inelastic effects in the material models used for low velocity impact simulations.

2 NUMERICAL FORMULATION

Following the continuum damage mechanics theory the damage in the form of micro-cracks impairs the load carrying capacity of the material. Suppose A_o is the undamaged loads bearing area and A_d is the damaged area of a representative volume of the material, an effective stress concept is introduced such that

$$\sigma = \left[1 - \frac{A_d}{A_o} \right] \sigma_e \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma = P/A_o$ is nominal stress and P is the nominal force applied to the representative volume. Effective stress, σ_e is defined as the stress in the remaining load bearing area and represented as

$$\sigma_e = \frac{P}{(A_o - A_d)} \quad (2)$$

The damage in the material is quantified in terms of its capacity to resist the applied load. Thus a damage variable, d is introduced in the following form

$$d = (A_d/A_o) \quad (3)$$

In the general 3D stress state, the effective stress can be written as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{M} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}_e \quad (4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = [\sigma_{11} \ \sigma_{22} \ \sigma_{33} \ \sigma_{23} \ \sigma_{13} \ \sigma_{12}]^T$ is the Voigt form of stress tensor having components in the principal orthotropic directions and \mathbf{M} is a transformation tensor or damage effect tensor. Using the principle of symmetrization the damage effect tensor is written as [2];

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} 1-D_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1-D_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1-D_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}[(1-D_{22})+(1-D_{33})] & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}[(1-D_{11})+(1-D_{33})] & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}[(1-D_{11})+(1-D_{22})] \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{33} are damage variables in fiber, in plane transverse and out of plane transverse directions.

Taking the nature of loading into consideration damage variables can be further elaborated

$$D_{11} = 1 - (1 - d_{1t})(1 - d_{1c}) \quad (6)$$

$$D_{22} = 1 - (1 - d_{2t})(1 - d_{2c}) \quad (7)$$

$$D_{33} = 1 - (1 - d_{2t})(1 - d_{2c}) \quad (8)$$

where d_{1t} , d_{1c} are damage variables for fiber tension and fiber compression; d_{2t} , d_{2c} are damage variables for matrix tension and matrix compression. These variables are assumed to be constant throughout the ply thickness.

The constitutive relationship between stress and strain for damage model is represented as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_e = \mathbf{E}_o : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e \quad (9)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_e = [\sigma_{e11} \ \sigma_{e22} \ \sigma_{e33} \ \sigma_{e23} \ \sigma_{e13} \ \sigma_{e12}]^T$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e = [\epsilon_{11}^e \ \epsilon_{22}^e \ \epsilon_{33}^e \ \epsilon_{23}^e \ \epsilon_{13}^e \ \epsilon_{12}^e]^T$ or

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{M} : \mathbf{E}_o : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e \quad (10)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{d}) : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{d})$ is second order constitutive tensor for damaged laminate and \mathbf{E}_o is for undamaged composite material.

For composite materials due to their transversely isotropic nature, the plastic potential function can be written [6][2] as

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_e) = \frac{1}{2} \left((\sigma_{e22} - \sigma_{e33})^2 + 4\sigma_{e23}^2 + 2a_{66}(\sigma_{e12}^2 + \sigma_{e13}^2) \right) \quad (12)$$

For computational implementation, it is beneficial to introduce the following form of above mentioned potential function

$$\mathbf{F}_p(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_e) = \left[\frac{1}{2} \left((\sigma_{e22} - \sigma_{e33})^2 + 4\sigma_{e23}^2 + 2a_{66}(\sigma_{e12}^2 + \sigma_{e13}^2) \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (13)$$

In plasticity theory, generally an equivalent stress is used to define the size and shape of plastic yield surface. Based on the presently defined potential function, equivalent stress can be defined as

$$\sigma^{eq} = \sqrt{3}f = \left[\frac{3}{2} \left((\sigma_{e22} - \sigma_{e33})^2 + 4\sigma_{e23}^2 + 2a_{66}(\sigma_{e12}^2 + \sigma_{e13}^2) \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (14)$$

Now the plastic yield function can be defined as

$$F_{yield}(\sigma^{eq}, \sigma_{flow}) = \sigma^{eq} - \sigma_{flow} = 0 \quad (15)$$

where σ_{flow} is the flow stress and controls the size of plastic yield surface. The plastic strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}^p$ can be defined using the associative flow rule as

$$\dot{\epsilon}^p = \dot{\lambda} \left(\frac{\partial F_{yield}}{\partial \sigma} \right) \quad (16)$$

where $\dot{\lambda}$ is the proportionality factor. This expression can be further elaborated as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11}^p \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22}^p \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{33}^p \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{23}^p \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{13}^p \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{12}^p \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\dot{\lambda}}{\sigma^{eq}} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{3}{2}(\sigma_{e22} - \sigma_{e33}) \\ \frac{3}{2}(\sigma_{e33} - \sigma_{e22}) \\ 6\sigma_{e23} \\ 3a_{66}\sigma_{e13} \\ 3a_{66}\sigma_{e12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Isotropic hardening is assumed to reduce the computational complexity. Without considering the strain rate effect, the flow stress can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{flow} = \left(\frac{\epsilon_{eq}^p}{A} \right)^{(1/n)} \quad (18)$$

where A and n are material parameters obtained by calibrating the experimental data. Equivalent plastic strain, ϵ_{eq}^p is calculated by equalizing the dissipation energy as following

$$\sigma_{eq} \epsilon_{eq}^p = \sigma : \epsilon^p \quad (19)$$

3 DAMAGE MODEL

3.1 Intra-laminar Damage Model

Hashin's failure criteria [7] is adopted to predict the intra-laminar damage initiation. The damage in the fiber or transverse direction is initiated as per following:

$$R_{1t} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{e11}}{S_{1t}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{e12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{e13}}{S_{13}} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{e11} \geq 0 \quad (20)$$

$$R_{1c} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{e11}}{S_{1c}} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{e11} < 0 \quad (21)$$

$$R_{2t} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{e22}}{S_{2t}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{e33}}{S_{2t}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{e23}^2 - \sigma_{e22}\sigma_{e33}}{S_{23}^2} \right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{e12}^2 + \sigma_{e13}^2}{S_{12}^2} \right) \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{e22} + \sigma_{e33} \geq 0 \quad (22)$$

where S_{1t} , S_{1c} are fiber direction tensile and compressive strength; S_{2t} is transverse direction tensile strength; S_{23} , S_{13} are out of plane shear strengths; S_{12} is in plane shear strength of a ply.

Matrix compression failure starts for unidirectional laminates in shear mode at fracture plane $\theta \sim 53^\circ$ with respect to direction of compression load [8] as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Stress states on fracture plane [9]

A stress based failure criterion for transverse compression, as per [10], is given as following

$$R_{2c} = \left(\frac{\sigma_t^n}{S_{23}^A + \mu_t^n \sigma_n^n} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_l^n}{S_{12} + \mu_l^n \sigma_n^n} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \sigma_{e22} + \sigma_{e33} < 0 \quad (23)$$

where the subscripts n, l and t refer to the normal, longitudinal and tangential direction with respect to the fracture plane direction. S_{12} is in-plane shear strength and S_{23}^A is shear strength in the fracture plane. S_{23}^A is calculated as

$$S_{23}^A = \frac{S_{2c}}{2} \left(\frac{1 - \sin \phi}{\cos \phi} \right) \quad (24)$$

where

$$\phi = 2\theta - 90^\circ \quad (25)$$

and S_{2c} is transverse direction compressive strength and μ_t^n and μ_l^n are friction coefficients based on Mohr-Coloumb failure theory which are calculated as

$$\mu_t^n = \tan(2\theta - 90^\circ) \quad (26)$$

and

$$\frac{\mu_t^n}{S_{23}^A} = \frac{\mu_l^n}{S_{12}} \quad (27)$$

These damage initiation threshold relations define the shape and size of damage surface in the effective stress space. Once the loading state reaches to a level of damage surface the damage in the ply is initiated. Now the growth of the damage surface is controlled by the damage propagation exponential function. Adopting the proposed damage growth function by Matzenmiller et al. [11], the fiber and matrix damage variable can be expressed as per following

$$d_i = 1 - \exp\left(\frac{1}{me} (1 - R_i)^m\right) \quad i \in [1t, 1c, 2t, 2c] \quad (28)$$

where m is material softening parameter and e is Napier's constant. The material softening parameter, m controls the post-damage behavior and plays an important role in resolving the problem of strain localization. Strain softening behavior of a material in FE analysis induces a strain localization problem. Due to this the solution depends on the size of an element. As the

material gets damaged, the softening starts with the continuous decrease of the stiffness with the increase of strain. The relatively low value of stiffness in the damaged region further causes high deformation of these damaged elements. Highly deformed elements in the mesh acts as a region of localized strain and this is also named as crack band. It is observed that the width of the crack band does not depend on the size of the element. To avoid strain localization, the fracture energy in the crack band is kept independent of size of the element. As per Bazant's crack band theory [12], the dissipated energy in the formation and opening of all microcracks per unit area of fracture surface, G_I is related to strain energy dissipated per unit volume, g_I as per following

$$G_I = g_I L_c \quad I \in [1t, 1c, 2t, 2c] \quad (29)$$

where G_{1t} and G_{1c} are mode-1 fracture toughness parameters related to intra-laminar fracture under tension and compression in the fiber direction and G_{2t} and G_{2c} are mode-1 fracture toughness parameters related to intra-laminar fracture under tension and compression in the transverse direction. The above mentioned relation can be further elaborated as

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_o \epsilon_o L_c + \int_{\epsilon_o}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2} \exp\left(\frac{1}{m\epsilon} (1 - R_i)^m\right) E^o \epsilon d\epsilon L_c \quad (30)$$

L_c is the characteristic length of the element. For a regular brick element, L_c is given as

- $L_c = L_x$ for fibre tension and compression
- $L_c = L_y$ for matrix tension
- $L_c = L_y / \cos \theta$ for matrix compression

where L_x and L_y are the length of element along fiber and transverse direction respectively. It is assumed that for matrix compression the failure occurs at a fracture angle, θ with the direction of applied load. Generally the value of θ is observed to be equal to 53° as per [8].

Using the relationships of characteristic lengths as defined earlier, eq. (30) can be numerically solved to calculate the value of m corresponding to a particular element size of regular shape. In order to avoid this way to solve this directly, the value of g_I is obtained by doing a FE analysis of a single element of a particular size and value of m is adjusted to satisfy the above mentioned equation.

3.2 Inter-laminar Damage Model

The inter-laminar damage is modeled using the cohesive surface formulation. Delamination initiation and propagation is simulated by defining a surface based interaction property, available in ABAQUS/Explicit, between the two plies. This surface based interaction defines the cohesive behavior between two adjacent plies, one of them is defined as master and other is the slave surface. Surface based cohesive interactions have the overall advantage than the conventional cohesive elements as these are easier to use and can significantly reduce the computational cost. The behavior of these two surfaces is characterized using traction-separation relation. A linear relationship between traction and relative displacement is defined which bonds the two surfaces (one master and other slave) together before the onset of delamination. The traction in a particular direction may or may not be coupled with relative displacements in the other direction. Without consideration of any coupling, the traction displacement law can be written as;

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{31} \\ \sigma_{32} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{33} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_{31} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{32} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta_{33} \\ \Delta_{31} \\ \Delta_{32} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

where 1,2 and 3 denotes the direction of a local coordinate system defined at cohesive surface such a way that direction-3 is aligned to normal direction to surface and direction-1 and 2 are along the surface. K_{33} is the out of plane stiffness and K_{31} , K_{32} are in-plane stiffnesses. These stiffnesses are used to control the relative displacements Δ_{33} , Δ_{31} and Δ_{32} between the master and slave surface corresponding to applied tractions σ_{33} , σ_{31} and σ_{32} . Ideally there should not be any relative deformation between the master and the slave surface prior to any kind of damage. But computationally, due to implemented contact algorithm, this scenario could not be avoided. A relatively high value of initial stiffness is generally specified to overcome this situation which may further lead to instability and convergence issues. There are various methods available in literature to define the initial stiffness. For the present study this value is defined as per following [13].

$$K_i = \frac{C_i}{10t_e} \quad i \in [33, 31, 32] \quad (32)$$

where C_i is equal to the tensile modulus, E_{33} for out of plane stiffess value and shear modulus, G_{13} and G_{23} for in plane stiffness value. t_e is thickness of adjacent element of cohesive surface. So the initial stiffness remain constant till the damage starts. The intra-laminar damage initiation criteria is defined based on maximum nominal stress. As per this, damage initiates when any of following condition is met;

$$\frac{\sigma_{33}}{\sigma_{33}^o} \geq 1 \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{31}}{\sigma_{31}^o} \geq 1 \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{32}}{\sigma_{32}^o} \geq 1 \quad (35)$$

Subscript 'o' indicates the initial state. After the initiation of inter-laminar damage, the stiffness degrades as per following

$$K_i = (1 - D)K_i^o \quad i \in [33, 31, 32] \quad (36)$$

Inter-laminar damage evolution laws are broadly classified into two categories; one type of evolution models are based on the total or plastic displacement in which damage variable is defined as the function of relative displacement; second type of evolution models are based on the fracture energy in which damage variable defined in terms of energy required for failure or delamination. Both of these are available in ABAQUS/Explicit. Out of these, energy based models show better delamination prediction capability [4] in case of transverse impact simulations and same is adopted in the present study. As per this the damage variable is varied in such a way that the area under the traction and separation remains equal to the fracture energy. The damage response can be linear or exponential and for the present study exponential damage behavior is adopted which shows better results as per an earlier study conducted by the authors [9]. Damage variable, D evolves as following:

$$D = \int_{\Delta_m^o}^{\Delta_m^f} \frac{\sigma_{eff}}{(G_c - G^o)} d\Delta \quad (37)$$

where Δ_m is the effective relative displacement used to describe the evolution of damage under the combination of normal and shear deformation across the interface. Subscript 'f' signifies the state of complete failure.

$$\Delta_m = \sqrt{(\Delta_{33})^2 + \Delta_{31}^2 + \Delta_{32}^2} \quad (38)$$

Similarly σ_{eff} is also defined as

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sqrt{(\sigma_{33})^2 + \sigma_{31}^2 + \sigma_{32}^2} \quad (39)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ is the Macaulay bracket; $\langle \Delta_{33} \rangle$ and $\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle$ signify that the compressive tractions do not lead to any separation of plies. G_c denotes the critical damage energy and G^o is the elastic energy at damage initiation. G_c and G^o are calculated using mixed-mode theory and can be determined using the two most common methods; one is power law and other is Benzeggagh-Kenane(BK) law. BK law is commonly recommended when the G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} are nearly equal [14]. So this law is adopted for the present study which defines G_c as

$$G_c = G_{Ic} + (G_{Sc} - G_{Ic}) \left(\frac{G_{Sc}}{G_{IIIc}} \right)^\eta \quad (40)$$

where η is a material parameter. From the often used values $\eta=1$ and $\eta=2$ [14], $\eta=1$ is adopted and found suitable for this study. $G_{Sc} = G_{IIc} + G_{IIIc}$ is the quantity signifying the total work done by shear tractions only. Using similar approach, the elastic energy corresponding to damage initiation, G^o can be calculated.

4 MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The material properties data for graphite/epoxy are adopted from [3] and [4]. Table 1 shows the basic properties for a graphite/epoxy ply. The plasticity parameters for graphite/epoxy material as shown in Table 2 are taken from [6]. Table 3 shows the fracture energies [3][4] for

Table 1: Elastic and strength properties for composite plate [3][4]

Modulus, Fiber direction, E_{11}	93.7(GPa)
Modulus, Transverse direction E_{22}, E_{33}	7.45(GPa)
Shear Modulus, Out of plane, G_{12}, G_{13}	3.97(GPa)
Shear Modulus, In plane, G_{23}	3.97(GPa)
Poisson's ratio, Out of plane μ_{12}, μ_{13}	0.26
Poisson's ratio, In plane μ_{23}	0.26
Density	1600(kg/m ³)
Tensile Strength, Fiber direction X_T	2945(MPa)
Tensile Strength, Transverse direction $Y_T=Z_T$	54(MPa)
Compressive Strength, Fiber direction X_C	1650(MPa)
Compressive Strength, Transverse direction $Y_C=Z_C$	240(MPa)
Shear failure strain, Out of plane $\epsilon_{12}^f, \epsilon_{13}^f$	5%
Shear failure strain, In plane ϵ_{23}^f	5%

Table 2: Inelastic Material Parameters [6]

a_{66}	1.25
A	0.9e-7
n	3.6

fiber and matrix material. Intra-laminar damage is simulated using cohesive surface interaction imposed between the two adjacent plies. Table 3 shows the cohesive properties assigned to define those interactions. Out of these, damage initiation tractions and the critical fracture energies for Mode-I, II and III are adopted from [15] whereas initial stiffnesses are calculated based on the ply material as per the eq.(32).

Table 3: Fracture Energies and Cohesive Parameters [3][4]

Fracture Energy	Value	Cohesive Parameters	Value
G_f^t	91.6(N/mm)	σ_{33}^o	30 (MPa)
G_f^c	79.9(N/mm)	σ_{13}^o	80 (MPa)
G_m^t	0.22(N/mm)	σ_{23}^o	80 (MPa)
G_m^c	0.76(N/mm)	G_{Ic}	520 (N/m)
		G_{IIc}	970 (N/m)
		G_{IIIc}	970 (N/m)
		K_{33}^o	1.2×10^{11} (N/mm)
		K_{31}^o	4.8×10^{10} (N/mm)
		K_{32}^o	4.8×10^{10} (N/mm)

Table 4: Values of Material Parameter, m used in softening law [2]

Element size (mm)	Fiber tension	Fiber compression	Matrix tension	Matrix compression
	m_f^t	m_f^c	m_m^t	m_m^c
$0.25 \times 0.25 \times 0.25$	0.225	0.07175	1.15	3
$0.5 \times 0.5 \times 0.5$	0.49	0.16	2.15	2.35
$1 \times 1 \times 1$	1.225	0.375	8.5	30
$2 \times 2 \times 2$	6.5	0.75	120	850

Next the material parameter, m for damage evolution model is determined by performing the analyses on single element model of various sizes. The value of m depends upon the direction as well as nature of loading so m_f^t , m_f^c , m_m^t and m_m^c for fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension and matrix compression are determined by comparing the corresponding fracture energies. The details of determining the m parameter for various subregions depending upon the element size is taken as per Table 4.

5 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

The numerical simulation of graphite/epoxy laminate under transverse impact load is performed using commercial software ABAQUS/Explicit. The constitutive formulation is implemented by developing a user defined subroutine called VUMAT. This subroutine updates the stress value at each material point corresponding to incremental strain value at each time step. The FE model is developed for $[0_3/90_3]_s$ laminate of actual size 65 mm \times 87.5 mm \times 2 mm. To reduce the computational time only quarter model is used. The frame used for holding the laminate for actual testing is also modeled which makes the actual opening of 45 mm \times 67.5 mm size. The indenter is modeled as ϕ 12.5 mm solid sphere of steel having 2.3 kg of mass. Steel frame and indenter is assigned with modulus of elasticity, E = 209 GPa and Poisson's ratio, $\nu=0.3$.

Figure 2: FE Model

Frame is modeled with standard density of steel, $\rho = 7830 \text{ kg/m}^3$ whereas density of sphere is adjusted so that the mass of indenter becomes 2.3 kg. Fine mesh of size $0.25 \text{ mm} \times 0.25 \text{ mm}$ is used for the near impact region whereas $1 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$ to $2 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$ element size is used for far impact region. A gripping pressure of 350 Pa is applied at the top surface of the frame as shown in Fig. 2. The bottom face of the frame is fixed in all directions. The symmetry boundary condition is applied at the two cut faces as shown in Fig. 2.

		Test	Simulation	
		[Aymerich et al.]	Plastic damage	Elastic damage
1 J	L (mm)	5.19	4.40	4.40
	W (mm)	5.17	4.80	5.08
2.1 J	L (mm)	8.62	8.40	9.10
	W (mm)	9.23	11.20	12.50
3.1 J	L (mm)	11.76	12.00	13.50
	W (mm)	12.35	13.60	15.10
3.9 J	L (mm)	15.19	14.00	15.00
	W (mm)	12.45	15.20	16.20
5.1 J	L (mm)	16.47	16.40	16.40
	W (mm)	14.90	17.60	18.60
6 J	L (mm)	18.30	18.80	19.20
	W (mm)	14.10	19.20	19.70
7 J	L (mm)	20.00	22.00	24.50
	W (mm)	15.02	20.80	20.80

Figure 3: Delamination area comparison

The cohesive surface interaction is used at 0/90 and 90/0 interface. Aymerich et al.[3] performed the testing of graphite/epoxy laminate under seven different levels of impact energies i.e. 1 J, 2.1 J, 3.1 J, 3.9 J, 5.1 J, 6 J and 7 J. In simulation the laminate is also checked for same impact energies. As per the test results reported by Aymerich et al. [3], the delamination mainly occurred at the bottom 0/90 interface. The experimental data was also compared by

Aymerich et al. [3] with the numerical results and reported the good match between two.

Figure 4: Delamination energy variation for 7J impact energy

In the present study delamination area is predicted by using both elastic damage model and plastic damage model and compared with experimental values. The delamination half width, W and half length, L are calculated as shown in Fig. 3 and compared with experiments. It is observed that the data matches more closely with the inelastic damage model as compared to

elastic damage model.

Figure 5: Variation of inter-laminar damage energy for various impact energies

Same behavior is found by observing more closely the damage prints as shown in Fig. 4. The delamination area predicted by elastic damage model is larger than the plastic damage model for all the energy levels and the results of plastic damage model match well with the experiments. The reason of larger delamination area in case of elastic damage model may

be due to the larger intra-laminar stresses which also lead to higher intra-ply tractions. This difference is more visible for 1 J impact energy levels whereas the delamination area is nearly same at 7 J impact energy. At high impact energy the intra-laminar damage due to matrix cracking also become significant and the intra-laminar damage region predicted by both elastic and plastic damage model is found nearly same. This may also lead to insignificant difference of delamination area at 7 J impact energy.

Figure 6: 1J impact energy

Figure 7: 7J impact energy

Various type of energy variation with respect to time are also checked for elastic and plastic damage model at 1 J and 7 J impact energies as shown in Fig. 6 and 7. This shows that plate absorbs significant amount of energy as plastic dissipation if the plastic damage model is used whereas the damage energy dissipation is lesser at 1 J impact energy. The damage energy dissipation at 7 J is nearly same whereas quite significant amount of plastic dissipation is observed. So nearly 50 % of the impact energy is dissipated in the form of permanent deformation and damage. The maximum contact force comparison as shown in Fig. 8 also demonstrates the good match for plastic damage model and also shows the importance of modeling the damage

induced inelasticity for low velocity impact simulations.

Figure 8: Force time history for impact energy from 1J to 7J

6 CONCLUSION

The constitutive model for FRP composite, which includes damage induced plasticity, was presented. This model demonstrated both the permanent deformation as well as delamination prediction capability at various impact energy levels i.e. 1 J, 2.1 J, 3.1 J, 3.9 J, 5.1 J, 6 J and 7 J. Following conclusions can be drawn on the basis of present study:

- At low impact energy levels, the elastic damage model overestimates the delamination area whereas the difference becomes insignificant at high impact energy levels.
- Significant energy is dissipated in the form of inelastic strain energy at 7 J impact energy. The difference in damage energy dissipation between the elastic and plastic damage model becomes vanishing as the impact energy increases.
- The elastic damage model over-predicts the maximum contact force whereas the predictions of plastic damage model are more closer to experiments.

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